

TEACHER'S CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT STYLE AND CLASSROOM CLIMATE AS FACTORS TO INCREASE LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT AMONG PUPILS LEARNING PROCESS AMIDST PANDEMIC

MYLA M. ALCAZAR

myla.alcazar@deped.gov.ph

0000-0002-4426-9955

Lusacan Elementary School, Tiaong, Quezon, Philippines
Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

A primary purpose of effective classroom management is to keep learners actively engage in the learning process. The management style of teachers can be a pathway or a barrier to better teaching and learning because particularly it is the crucial part of active engagement in the learning process. The study was limited to the teacher's classroom management style and climate as factors to increase level of teacher's engagement at the midst of pandemic among pupils learning process in the District of Tiaong, Division of Quezon. Purposive sampling technique was used in this study with one hundred four (104) elementary teachers from the said district. The findings of the study were the teachers' engagement to increase the learning process has significantly related with the teachers' classroom management style, classroom climate and teacher's engagement and there is a significant difference in the perceptions of the respondents when grouped according to schools on the following variables: classroom management style, classroom climate and teacher's engagement therefore, the hypotheses were rejected. The recommendations where the teachers may enroll their master's degree and finish it for their professional growth and for the promotion purposes so that they can use it to their promotion. However, the teacher's engagement may use another strategy on how they can personally involve to the learning of their students. Moreover, the classroom climate will focus to the strength of the students give them the environment that they can feel that they are safe at the same time they are learning, thus the personal problem of the teacher may set aside during the learning and teaching process so that the environment for learning will set in the positive climate.

Keywords: Teacher's Classroom Management Style, Classroom Climate and Teacher's Engagement